

We are glad to welcome you to SCENARIOS' third newsletter!

SCENARIOS is a 4-year H2020 Research and Innovation project (RIA) involving 19 partners from 10 European countries and Israel. The goal is to close the knowledge gap and achieve breakthrough TRL advances in the toxicology, detection and remediation of probably the most objectionable and widespread class of contaminants -PFAS-, with an unprecedented energetic balance and virtually no external chemical additives. A major effort is underway to develop Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) of PFAS, including the new generation of congeners, to assist EC and EU countries in decision-making on these substances for environmental safety and human health.

SCENARIOS looks back at its achievements in the third year

The SCENARIOS project has made significant advancements in smart detection technologies for PFAS. Surface Enhanced Raman Scattering (SERS) detection has achieved a detection limit of 5 ppt for both long- and short-chain PFAS, showcasing its advanced sensitivity and meeting one of project main scientific and technological objectives. Additionally, electrochemical microsensors have been developed with detection limits in the ppb range, providing another promising approach for PFAS detection. These technologies have currently reached Technology Readiness Level 3 (TRL 3). The next phase of the project focuses on scaling up at least one of these technologies for validation and demonstration at Demo site 1, dedicated to biomonitoring efforts in the Alessandria region of Italy. These developments represent critical progress toward practical and effective PFAS detection in real-world applications.

Within the SCENARIOS project, the systematic investigation of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) toxicity through a systems toxicology lens has gained momentum, largely due to evidence of their persistence, bioaccumulative properties, and associated health concerns. By combining a suite of "omics" platforms—physiomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics—SCENARIOS endeavors to elucidate the molecular pathways that drive PFAS-induced effects. Recent work testing over 30 distinct PFAS congeners, chosen to represent the diversity of terminal products and evaluated in both 2D and 3D human cell models, uncovered a shared molecular signature converging on the retinoid X receptor (RXR) pathway. This unified profile points to a mechanism linking organ-level toxicity with immunological perturbations, highlighting the power of a systems-level approach for comprehensively characterizing the hazards posed by PFAS.

Within the SCENARIOS project, the quasi zero-energy PFAS remediation pillar is dedicated to developing and validating novel remediation approaches for contaminated sites. At the Korsør demonstration site in Denmark, Surface Active Foam Fractionation (SAFF) successfully removed short-chain PFAS from groundwater, yielding strong performance for congeners longer than C4. Meanwhile, cold plasma destruction of PFAS—proven effective at TRL3 — is poised for demonstration in tandem with SAFF at pilot sites in Sweden and Spain, where it will target landfill leachate and drinking water, respectively.

In addition, SCENARIOS continues to advance both its PFAS remediation solutions and in silico toxicology assessment methods toward pre-commercial readiness, underpinned by thorough life cycle and cost evaluations. Physiologically based kinetic (PBK) modeling has been introduced to correlate in vitro hazard data with in vivo exposure conditions, bridging the gap between laboratory findings and real-world scenarios for more informed risk assessment within the project's framework.

These measures ensure that emerging technologies are both environmentally responsible and economically feasible. Parallel efforts in exploitation and industrialization—bolstered by SCENARIOS' involvement in the Horizon Results Booster program—accelerate the transition from proof-of-concept to market deployment for the project's key enabling technologies. Further amplifying impact, a robust dissemination and communication strategy has showcased SCENARIOS' concepts and findings on scientific, educational, and commercial platforms, with multiple events fostering meaningful exchanges and expanding awareness of SCENARIOS' innovations in PFAS remediation and toxicological risk assessment.

NEWS

SCENARIOS at Water Treatment Europe 2024

The international water research community gathered this week at BluePoint in Brussels, for WaterProjectsEurope, a key component of WaterKnowledgeEurope2024, bringing together 70 experts from scientific, policy, and industrial sectors.

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High School Students Explore Environmental Remediation Strategies in Valencia

On October 18, students at Colegio Santa Ana y San José de la Montaña in Albal, Valencia, gained unique insights into environmental remediation through an engaging scientific presentation by Natividad Isabel Navarro Pacheco from the University of Castilla-La Mancha (UCLM).

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SCENARIOS at IVS-IPSTA 2024

On 28th October Meghna Khadka from Ben Gurion University of the Negev attended and presented her work on electrochemical detection of PFAS at the 41th Annual IVS-IPSTA 2024-Conference that was held in Tel Aviv University in Tel Aviv, Israel.

Around 200 scientists, engineers, and researchers from government laboratories and universities gather for this worldwide conference to present results and challenges in a variety of formats. It brings together research and technology from the domains of solid state and materials engineering to provide a venue for knowledge sharing and learning about transdisciplinary achievements.

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SCENARIOS at ALVA annual conference in food safety

The Luxembourg Veterinary and Food Administration (ALVA) recently had its annual conference on research in food safety: Contaminants in the food chain. This year the event was held in-person in the Coque Auditorium in Kirchberg (Luxembourg) on Thursday 10th October. It was an opportunity to connect with fellow professionals, researchers, and experts: the conference was followed by a reception to foster collaborations within Luxembourg and beyond with invited speakers from our neighbouring countries, with approximately 100-150 people attending the event.

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SCENARIOS at EUROTOX 2024

The Danish Society of Toxicology and Pharmacology organized EUROTOX 2024 in Copenhagen. The congress took place from 8th to 11th September and gathered over a thousand people at Denmark's capital. The congress theme "Toxicology - A Quest for safe Chemicals and Medicines" reflects the congress programme including a variety of topics dealing with safety of drugs and environmental chemicals, new and emerging technologies, personalised medicine, human health effects caused by exposure to chemicals as well as safety issues arising from climate changes.

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SCENARIOS at EuSP2024 and GSAC2024

SCENARIOS was represented at the 3rd European Sample Preparation Conference (EuSP2024) and the 2nd Green and Sustainable Analytical Chemistry Conference (GSAC2024) a joint conferences event that took place from the 15th to the 18th September in Crete, Greece and gathered around 230 participants. The goal of the 3rd European Sample Preparation Conference (EuSP2024) and 2nd Green and Sustainable Analytical Chemistry Conference (GSAC2024) is to showcase innovative research, cutting-edge technologies, and new methodologies in the fields of sample preparation and sustainable analytical chemistry.

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SCENARIOS at Albacete's Regional Fair

On 17th September 2024, our colleague, Natividad Isabel Navarro Pacheco from University of Castilla-La Mancha (UCLM) participated in the Albacete fair at the UCLM stand. She presented their work in the SCENARIOS project to civil society and the general public which were quite attracted to the explanation delivered during the project work presentation and wanted to understand the efforts carried out in the project better.

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SCENARIOS at World Groundwater Congress 2024

The International Association of Hydrogeologists organized the World Groundwater Congress 2024 from the 8th to the 13th of September at The Congress Centre in the city of Davos in Switzerland. It was oriented to the scientific community, policy makers, industry representatives and civil society with around 150 attendees from these interested groups.

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Korsør workshop: "PFAS remediation in action: sustainable solutions and acceptance conditions"

On the 3rd and 4th September the project held two workshops with the title "PFAS remediation in action: sustainable solutions and acceptance conditions" with experts from all around the world as speakers and attendees. Project coordinator Prof. Francesco Dondero from Università degli Studi del Piemonte Orientale opened the event and let us know his views on current PFAS challenges: the three knots of detection, impact assessment and remediation.

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SCENARIOS at IS-WRA

Samuel Kolade, PhD student from the Department of Environmental Hydrology and Microbiology at the Zuckerkberg Institute for Water Research at Ben Gurion University of the Negev, basion University, presented the work he is doing on PFAS to over 100 participants from industry, policy makers and the scientific community at the Israeli Association for Water Resources Annual Conference during its 2024 edition. The event took place at Weizmann Institute of Science in Rehovot in Israel on the 18th June.

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SCENARIOS and ZeroPol2030

SCENARIOS was present at the living lab "Designing strategies for better governance of persistent chemicals in the Black Sea basin" thought the attendance of our colleague Mihaela Mirea from Lomartov. The gathering was held on the 28th and 29th May in Varna, Bulgaria.

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SCENARIOS at ISE 36

During the 36th Topical Meeting International Society of Electrochemistry: "Marine and environmental electrochemistry in the era of new technologies" that was held in Šibenik, Croatia our student Meghna Khadka, from Ben Gurion University of the Negev, participated with an oral presentation of the work carried out at their lab.

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Students check on UCLM laboratories SCENARIOS work

On the 22nd May between 11:00 and 13:00 hours our colleagues from Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha working in SCENARIOS participated in an activity called 'Feel like a scientist for one day' at the UCLM. Thirty students from a high school in the Region of Castilla-La Mancha (Spain) came to the laboratory to see the work carried out in the lab and learn more about SCENARIOS's work and goals. The activity was and student asked a lot of questions and showed genuine curiosity.

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SCENARIOS at ENMF 4th

The 4th ENMF (Exploring Novel Medical Frontiers) Multi-Disciplinary Medical Conference, held on May 17-19, 2024, at the Nikolaos Germanos Conference Center in Thessaloniki, aimed to continue the successful collaboration of distinguished scientists from previous conferences. Organized by the Center for Research and Innovation in Solid Organ Transplantation of the Aristotelian University of Thessaloniki, the Neurosurgery Institute of the University of Ioannina, and the Department of Nuclear Medicine of Hippocraton General Hospital of Thessaloniki, the conference focused on "Medico-Surgical Innovations, Imaging Breakthroughs, and Artificial Intelligence".

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SCENARIOS at SETAC

Project coordinator Prof. Francesco Dondero and SCENARIOS scientist Dr. Tommaso Serchi organized and chaired the session on PFAS toxicology at the ongoing SETAC2024 meeting in Sevilla, Spain. In the morning of Tuesday 07th a brainstorming by more experienced scientists illuminated the path to decipher the complexity of PFAS toxicology. The session extended in the afternoon with young PhD students and postdocs presenting their latest findings. Amazing session!

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Joint workshop on remediation of forever chemicals

On the 10th April SCENARIOS participated in the joint webinar "Remediating contaminated sites by persistent, mobile and toxic substances: H2020 projects case studies & results" that was organized in conjunction with sister project Promissces and ZeroPolm with the help of the Horizon Results booster. The opening of the session was by Sofia Finzi from the Horizon Results Booster, followed by a short introduction by Sarah Hale from the German Water Center that spoke about the contribution of European research to evidence based zero pollution and health policy.

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SCENARIOS at IZM2024

During the 4th Italian Zebrafish Meeting IZM2024 that was held in Palermo from the 7th to the 9th February, we had the occasion to present SCENARIOS project and the first results obtained using the zebrafish model. The meeting provides a forum for presentation and discussion of the most innovative and exciting research currently ongoing in Italy using the zebrafish model. The opportunity for our project arose when a poster was selected for presentation during the meeting.

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Innovative Apps for a Greener Future: The SCENARIOS Project's Digital Solutions for Environmental Health through deep learning

Bringing technology and healthcare, the SCENARIOS project, funded by the EU's Horizon 2020, pioneers advancements in risk assessment and environmental health through synergistically blending computational chemistry, cheminformatics and machine learning, with deep learning. It introduces innovative tools for predicting molecular biological target interactions and compound cytotoxicity, aligning with the European Green Deal's toxin-free vision.

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PUBLICATIONS & RESULTS

In the last year the efforts in the project have as a result another nine scientific publications, and SCENARIOS collaborated in the writing of the Policy Brief for achieving zero pollution:

- Sensitive and Accurate Determination of 32 PFAS in Human Serum Using Online SPE- UHPLC- HRMS [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Bioconversion of polystyrene and food waste streams into biochar: an upgraded enzymatic activation system [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- A Review on Removal and Destruction of Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances (PFAS) by Novel Membranes [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Impact of Legacy Perfluorooctane Sulfonate (PFOS) and Perfluorooctanoate (PFOA) on GABA Receptor-Mediated Currents in Neuron-Like Neuroblastoma Cells: Insights into Neurotoxic Mechanisms and Health Implications [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Evaluation of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) toxic effects on the acute inflammatory response in the medicinal leech Hirudo verbana [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Policy Brief Achieving zero pollution by 2050 needs regulatory change: a call for policy support of New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Managing Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substance (PFAS) Contamination in Agricultural Soils: Investigating Remediation Approaches in Non-conventional Agriculture [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Study of global PFAS pollution levels in fish from the United Kingdom and their impact on human health through diet [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Assessing Apical Toxicity and Sublethal Responses of Earthworms in PFAS-Contaminated Soils: A Comprehensive Study at a Fire Training Site in Sweden [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- Parameter grouping and co-estimation in physiologically based kinetic models using genetic algorithms [▶ LEARN MORE](#)

FORTHCOMING ACTIVITIES

- Catalunya, Spain**
A demonstration of short-chain PFAS removal using Surface Active Foam Fractionation (SAFF) will take place during February-March 2025.
Contact us for more information!
- Trelleborg, Sweden**
Experience a full-scale demonstration of SAFF for PFAS removal from landfill leachate, combined with PFAS destruction via Cold Plasma. The event will run from February to July 2025.
- SCENARIOS Summer School**
Exciting news! The SCENARIOS Summer School is launching soon. Stay tuned for the Save the Date announcement!

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Be the first to learn about project events and activities!
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<https://scenarios-project.eu/>

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